

Dorabella Chiper Solution

author Alessandro Boatto
email: alessandroboatto1@gmail.com

Abstract

«The Enigma I will not explain – its “dark saying” must be left unguessed, and I warn you that the apparent connection between the Variations and the Theme is often of the slightest texture; further, through and over the whole set another and larger theme “goes”, but is not “played”.»

- Sir Edward Elgar

«There is nothing to be gained in an artistic or musical sense by solving the enigma of any of the personalities; the listener should hear the music as music, and not trouble himself with any intricacies of “programme”. To me, the various personalities have been a source of inspiration, their idealizations a pleasure – and one that is intensified as the years go by.»

-Sir Edward Elgar

Proof and solution

One of the most famous compositions of Sir Edward Elgar are the Enigma Variations. Sir Edward Elgar made it clear that there is another hidden theme that is not heard, and is hidden within the message in **Fig.1**.

The Main Theme is :

Message and solution :

Fig.1

- 1- The message in Fig.1 is made up of three rows and a signature.
- 2- Each row represents a work by Sir Edward Elgar before the year 1897.
- 3- The first row at the top is made up of 29 symbols and represents the work 29 (Op.29).
- 4- The second row in the middle is made up of 31 symbols and represents the work 31 (Op.31).
- 5- The third row below is made up of 27 symbols and represents the work 27 (Op.27).

Op.29 is titled "The light of life"

Op.31 is titled "After"

Op.27 is titled "The dance"

The hidden message is :

The light of life after the dance

Another proof : *The title and the symbols*

546 NINETEENTH SATURDAY CONCERT.

This is followed by :—

No. 3. *2nd Violin & Cello.*

—leading eventually to the “second subject” :—

No. 4. *Viole con sordini e Corni.*

The “working out” section, commencing :—

No. 5. *Alligro ma non troppo.*

—is chiefly occupied with the development of the “first subject,” freely treated. To this succeeds an independent episode :—

No. 6. *Alligretto pastorale.*

Arpa. *Corno.*

—which is subsequently heard in combination with the “second subject.”

An *Alligro marziale*, evolved from, the two principal subjects, and commencing thus :—

No. 7. *Animato.*

f *Violini.*

—brings the work—after a return to No. 2—to a brilliant and triumphant end.

[C. A. B.]

19 Symbols

Nineteenth symbols and the title is : Nineteenth Saturday Concert

Conclusion

«There is nothing to be gained in an artistic or musical sense by solving the enigma of any of the personalities; the listener should hear the music as music, and not trouble himself with any intricacies of “programme”. To me, the various personalities have been a source of inspiration, their idealizations a pleasure – and one that is intensified as the years go by.» - Sir Edward Elgar

Sir Edward Elgar

Miss Dora Penny (Dorabella)

